

The Effectiveness of Interactive Teaching Methods in Enhancing Students' Learning Outcomes in Biology

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the effectiveness of interactive teaching methods in enhancing students' learning outcomes in Biology in Calabar Municipality Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Quasi-Experimental Research Design using pre-test post-test non-randomized control group design was used. The population of the study comprised of all the 1458 Biology students in the eighteen (18) Public Secondary Schools in Calabar Municipality Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. The Simple Random Sampling Technique of balloting was used to select two schools, one school for experimental group and one school for control group. The first school was assigned interactive teaching method while the other school was assigned Lecture method (control group), all using intact class setting. The sample size used for the study was Ninety-Two (92) Senior Secondary Two Biology Students drawn from two schools using intact class setting. 44 students were exposed to experimental group (Interactive teaching method) while 48 students were exposed to control group respectively (Lecture method). The research instrument was an instructional treatment package on The Human Digestive System and Biology Achievement Test (BAT). The instruments were subject to face validity with a 20 item questions. Kuder Richardson formula-21 was used to determine the internal consistency for Biology Achievement Test (BAT) which yielded a reliability Co-efficient of 80. Mean and Standard Deviation was used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA) was used to analyze the data. The findings of the study revealed a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using interactive method and those taught using traditional method. There was no significant interaction effect of methods and gender on posttest mean achievement of students in Biology. It was recommended among other things that teachers should embrace the 21st century skills by utilizing diverse innovative pedagogies which will enable them to gain better experience in their teaching profession thus improving the learning outcomes of students.

Keywords: *Interactive teaching method, Students learning outcomes.*

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Introduction

Teaching methods play a crucial role in shaping the learning outcomes of students at the secondary level. Over the years, traditional lecture-style teaching has been the norm in secondary education institutions. However, with the advent of technology and changing pedagogical approaches,

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interactive teaching methods have gained increasing attention for their potential to enhance student engagement and improve learning outcomes. Interactive teaching methods refer to instructional techniques that actively engage students in the learning process, encouraging their participation, collaboration, and critical thinking (Afzal & Rafiq, 2022). These methods go beyond passive listening to lectures and involve students in active learning activities, such as discussions, group work, simulations, case studies, role plays, and problem-solving exercises. Interactive teaching methods create an environment where students are actively involved in constructing their knowledge, rather than just receiving information passively (Rafiq, Afzal & Kamran, 2022).

Research has shown that interactive teaching methods have a positive impact on student learning outcomes at the secondary level. They promote deep learning, critical thinking skills, and higher-order cognitive skills, such as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. These methods also foster greater student engagement, motivation, and retention of knowledge. Moreover, interactive teaching methods promote active participation, collaboration, and communication skills, which are crucial for success in the 21st-century workforce (Rafiq, Afzal & Kamran, 2022). One of the key advantages of interactive teaching methods is their ability to cater to diverse learning styles and preferences of students. They provide opportunities for students to learn at their own pace, reflect on their learning, and receive timely feedback from peers and instructors.

Biology as one of the science subject is defined as study of life and concern itself with the study of structure, behaviour, distribution, the origin of plants and animals and their relationships with their environment. Biology as the branch of science and the prerequisite subject for many fields of learning contributes immensely to the technological growth of the nation. This include medicine, forestry, agriculture, biotechnology and nursing. With global scientific and technological growth occurring rapidly, students' interest in biology is the major problems. Therefore, it is very important that man knows about the nature and the phenomenon surrounded him and consequences of the interactions between man and his environment.

The objectives which guide the formulation of practical Biology curriculum includes; -secondary school science laboratories which serve as a conducive environment for practical work- a source of teaching and learning in science where students are able to carry out science process skills, practical work in school laboratory gives students appreciation of the spirit of method of problem solving, analytical and generalization ability, practical work foster students positive attitudes toward science and maintains their interest in the learning of science subjects.

Interactive methods are based on the principles of interaction, student activity, reliance on group experience, and mandatory feedback. An environment of educational communication is created, which is characterized by openness, interaction of participants, equality of their arguments, the accumulation of joint knowledge, the possibility of mutual assessment and control. The leader (teacher, trainer), along with new knowledge, leads the participants in the study to an independent search. The activity of the teacher gives way to the activity of students, his task is to create conditions for their initiative. The teacher refuses the role of a kind of filter that passes educational information through himself, and serves as an assistant in the work.

The National Academy of Sciences (2010) recommended that interactive teaching method was found to achieve higher than the non-interactive method in biology. The use of practical activities (approach) to the teaching of biology should be utilized by teachers so as to produce students who can acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and scientific competence needed to meet the scientific and technological demands of the society. Khan and Iqbal (2011) carried out a study in Pakistan and found out that, the students taught through interactive teaching method show more performance in science process skill than the students of the control group taught through traditional teaching method. Also, Nwosu and Okeke (2017) study on effect of interactive method on secondary school students' achievement in Biology" also supports the finding. This research

showed that students who participated in interactive method performed better in post-tests compared to those who were taught using the traditional classroom method.

Nzewi (2008) and Aina (2012) observed that the interactive method of teaching is an indispensable approach that should be utilized by science teachers and that if effective teaching and learning of science subjects are to be achieved interactive approach of teaching must be set apart for practical or experimental studies to take place". Ude and Onah (2017) said, "It helps the students gain more understanding on science concepts especially as most science concepts are abstract in nature. In the same vein, Oyedeji (2000) laments that the use of traditional lecture method of "chalk and talk" has gained prominence in the teaching of biology than practical method. The author discovered that students taught with science Laboratory Instructional Strategy performed significantly better than use of traditional lecture method.

Apart from the interactive method of teaching, gender is also implicated in students' academic achievement in biology. Gender refers to the roles and responsibilities of men and women that are created in family, societies and culture. The concept of gender is the expectations held about characteristics, attitudes, and likely behaviour of both men and women (masculinity and femininity) in the society (Ezeh, 2013). There is a general belief among Nigerians that boys are superior to girls in terms of physical build up, intelligence and reasoning. According to Okeke (2007) gender and gender stereotyping have brought discrimination in academic achievement which is a matter of great concern to educationist.

Ukozor (2011) found that gender influences male students' conceptual in favour of the female. Also, Archer and Macrae in Iwuji (2012) stated that males' students appear to be higher in achievement than the females and also reported that boys are better at activities requiring manipulation (psychomotor skills) than girls, and that boys are more aggressive towards laboratory and project work. A study carried out by Iwuji (2012) stated that boys also perform better than girls in process of measuring and experimenting. The finding of the study is also supported by Oakley in Iwuji (2012) who opined that right from the childhood, a boy traditionally receives more training and encouragement for achievement than girls. Similarly, Nwachukwu and Eze (2020) studied the effect of teaching strategies and gender on students' performance in Biology, the researchers concluded that there was no significant interaction effect between the teaching method and gender on students' performance in Biology. The study affirmed that both male and female students benefited similarly from different teaching methods.

Theoretical Framework

The theory that is considered relevant to this study is Jean Piaget's Theory of Cognitive Development (1936). Jean Piaget's theory of cognitive development focuses on how learners interact with their environment to develop complex reasoning and knowledge. The Swiss psychologist, Jean Piaget, introduced a developmental epistemology that focused on the growth of intelligence from infancy to adulthood. Piaget's theory is influenced by the following ideas. These ideas helped Piaget to develop his basic assumptions which forms the foundation of his theory. The first is that intelligence like a biological system, constructs the structures it needs to function. Second, knowledge is the interaction between the individual and the environment. Third, the growth of intelligence is influenced by four factors namely, physical environment, social environment, maturation and equilibrium. This theory is relevant to this study in the sense that, interaction with one's physical and social environment is essential for cognitive development. For example, playing with new objects and toys and also experimenting in the science laboratories are ways to develop students' knowledge which will lead to academic performance of students.

Statement of the Problem

The conventional/traditional teaching methods involve unidirectional flow of information/knowledge from teacher to the students and do not encourage process skill acquisition needed for proper understanding of biological principles, concepts and facts. The unidirectional flow of information in the traditional teaching method makes students passive and unable to construct meaningful knowledge in the teaching and learning of Biology. The shortcomings of these traditional teaching methods resulted to the persistent search for an effective method of teaching and learning of Biology concepts. The researcher is of the opinion the use of innovative teaching methods such as interactive method of teaching can be considered as an effective teaching methods that can improve students' achievement and interest in Biology.

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated the Effect of Interactive Method of Teaching on the Academic Achievement of Students in Biology. The study addressed the following research questions.

- a. What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using interactive method and those taught with traditional method?
- b. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Biology across the teaching methods (interactive method and traditional method)?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated and tested at $\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using interactive method and those taught with traditional method.
2. There is no significant interaction effect of methods and gender on students' achievement in Biology.

Method

The study adopted quasi-experimental research design using pre-test post-test non-randomized group control design. The study was conducted in Calabar Municipality Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. The study population comprised all the 1458 students in the eighteen (18) public secondary schools in Calabar Municipality. The simple random sampling technique of balloting was used to select one school for experimental group (interactive method) and one school for control group (lecture method) making a total of two schools, all using intact class setting. The sample size used for the study was Ninety-Two (92) Senior Secondary Two Biology Students drawn from two schools using intact class setting. 44 students were exposed to experimental group (Interactive teaching method) while 48 students were exposed to control group respectively (Lecture method). An instructional treatment package on the human digestive system and biology achievement test (BAT) were the two instruments used for study. Biology Performance Test (BPT) was trial tested on twenty (25) SS2 students who were not part of the main study. The instruments were used for pre-test and post-test. The instruments were subject to face and content validity with a 20 item questions submitted to two Lecturers, one Biology expert and one expert from test and measurement. The reliability of the study was obtained using Kuder Richardson formula-21 to determine the internal consistency for Biology Achievement Test (BAT) which yield reliability Co-efficient of 80. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using interactive method and those taught with traditional method?

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation of Pretest and Posttest Scores of Students Taught Biology Using Interactive Method and Those Taught Using Traditional Method

Variable	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Interactive Method	44	14.60	4.31	24.30	6.58	9.70
Traditional Method	48	13.94	3.87	18.90	6.13	4.96

Results in table 1 show that the group taught Biology using Interactive method had a pretest mean of 14.60 with a standard deviation of 4.31 and a posttest mean of 24.30 with a standard deviation of 6.58. The difference between the pretest and posttest mean was 9.70. The group taught Biology using traditional method had a pretest mean of 13.94 with a standard deviation of 3.87 and a posttest mean of 18.90 with a standard deviation of 6.13. The difference between the pretest and posttest mean was 4.96. However, for each of the groups, the posttest means was greater than the pretest means with the group taught using Interactive method having a higher mean gain. This is an indication that Interactive method has more effect on students' achievement in Biology than the traditional method.

Research Question 2

What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Biology across the teaching methods (interactive method and traditional method)?

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation of Pretest and Posttest Scores of Students Taught Biology across the Teaching Methods (Interactive Method and Traditional Method)

Variable	Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean gain
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Interactive	Male	20	14.00	3.32	23.86	7.12	9.86
	Female	24	15.36	5.30	24.86	5.95	9.50
Traditional	Male	26	14.00	4.24	19.77	6.39	5.77
	Female	22	13.86	3.39	17.73	5.69	3.87

Results in table 2 show the effect of students' gender on students' achievement in Biology using interactive method. Result shows that the male students had a pretest mean of 14.00 with a standard deviation of 3.32 and a posttest mean of 23.86 with a standard deviation of 7.12. The difference between the pretest and posttest mean for the male students was 9.86. The female students had a pretest mean of 15.36 with a standard deviation of 5.30 and a posttest mean of 24.86 with a standard deviation of 5.95. The difference between the pretest and posttest mean was 9.50.

Results also show that the male students under traditional method had a pretest mean of 14.00 with a standard deviation of 4.24 and a posttest mean of 19.77 with a standard deviation of 6.39. The difference between the pretest and posttest mean was 5.77. The female students under traditional method had a pretest mean of 13.86 with a standard deviation of 3.39 and a posttest mean of 17.73 with a standard deviation of 5.69. The difference between the pretest and posttest

mean was 3.87. However, for each of the groups, the posttest means were greater than the pretest means with the female students having a higher mean gain than the male students. This is an indication that students' gender has influences on the methods used in teaching Biology.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using interactive method and those taught with traditional method.

Table 3. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the Mean Achievement Scores of Students Taught Biology Using Interactive Method and Those Taught Using Traditional Method

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	783.361 ^a	2	391.680	9.699	.000
Intercept	4319.977	1	4319.977	106.976	.000
Pretest	41.125	1	41.125	1.018	.315
Methods	765.828	1	765.828	18.964	.000
Error	3997.894	89	40.383		
Total	52146.000	92			
Corrected Total	4781.255	91			

Note: a. R Squared = .159 (Adjusted R Squared = .142)

The results in table 3 showed that the significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using Interactive method and those taught using traditional method. Results show that with respect to the groups taught Biology using Interactive method and those taught using traditional method, an F-ratio of 18.964 was obtained with associated probability value of 0.000. Since the associated probability value of 0.00 was less than 0.05 set as level of significance, the null hypothesis (H01) which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using interactive method and those taught with traditional method is rejected. Thus, inference drawn therefore is that there was a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using interactive method and those taught with traditional method with those taught using interactive method having a higher mean gain. This shows that interactive method has more effect on students' achievement in Biology than the traditional method.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant interaction effect of methods and gender on students' achievement in Biology.

Table 4. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the Significant Interaction Effect of Methods and Gender on Students' Achievement in Biology

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	808.419 ^a	4	202.105	4.935	.001
Intercept	4032.398	1	4032.398	98.454	.000
Pretest	.914	1	.914	.022	.882
Methods	778.997	1	778.997	19.020	.000
Gender	6.636	1	6.636	.162	.688
Methods * Gender	58.295	1	58.295	1.423	.236
Error	3972.836	87	40.957		
Total	52146.000	92			
Corrected Total	4781.255	91			

Note: a. R Squared = .171 (Adjusted R Squared = .133)

Results in table 4 show that an F-ratio of 1.423 with associated probability value of 0.236 was obtained for interaction between methods and gender on students' achievement in Biology. Since the associated probability value of 0.23 was greater than 0.05 set as level of significance, the null hypothesis (H_{03}) which stated that there is no statistically significant interaction effect of methods and gender on students' achievement in Biology was retained. Thus, inference drawn is that there was no significant interaction effect of methods and gender on posttest mean achievement of students in Biology.

Discussion of Findings

Interactive Method and Students' Academic Achievement in Biology

The results in table 1 and 2 showed that there was a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using interactive method and those taught using traditional method with those taught using interactive method having a higher mean gain. This shows that interactive method has higher effect on students' achievement in Biology than the traditional method. These results agree with the findings of Nwosu and Okeke (2017) study on effect of interactive method on secondary school students' achievement in Biology. This research showed that students who participated in interactive method performed better in post-tests compared to those who were taught using the traditional classroom method. Also, Khan and Iqbal (2011) study in Pakistan, found out that, the students taught through interactive teaching method show more performance in science process skill than the students of the control group taught through traditional teaching method.

Interaction Effect of Methods, Students' Gender and Academic Achievement in Biology

Table 3 and 4 shows that there was no significant interaction effect of methods and gender on posttest mean achievement of students in Biology. These findings agreed with the findings of Nwachukwu and Eze (2020) study on the effect of teaching strategies and gender on students' performance in Biology, the researchers concluded that there was no significant interaction effect between the teaching method and gender on students' performance in Biology. The study affirmed that both male and female students benefited similarly from different teaching methods.

Conclusion

Interactive teaching method have the power to transform the classroom into a dynamic student-centered environment that fosters academic excellence and lifelong learning. By incorporating interactive teaching methods, biology teachers can create a more engaging, effective, and enjoyable learning classroom experience.

Recommendation

There is the need for teachers to embrace the 21st century skills by utilizing diverse innovative pedagogies which will enable them to gain better experience in their teaching profession thus improving the learning outcomes of students.

References

- Afzal, A., & Rafiq, S. (2022). Impact of teachers' instructional techniques on student involvement in class: A case study. *UMT Education Review*, 5(2), 184–204. <https://doi.org/10.32350/uer.52.10>
- Aina, K. J. (2012). Challenges and prospects of primary science teaching in Nigeria. *Continental Journal of Education Research*, 5(2), 32–37.
- Ezeh, D. N. (2013). Science without woman: A paradox. 75th inaugural lecture delivered on Monday 30th in University of Nigeria Nsukka. Published by the University of Nigeria Senate Ceremony Committee.
- Iwuji, T. C. (2012). Effect of laboratory method on students' achievement and retention in senior secondary schools in Kogi East Senatorial Zone. *Journal of Research and Method in Education*, 8(6), 31–39.
- National Academy of Sciences. (2010). *A new biology for the 21st century: Ensuring the United States leads the coming biology revolution*. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press. Retrieved from <http://www.nap.edu>
- Nzewi, U. M. (2008). Practical approach to the effective teaching of ecological concepts for sustainable development. *Science Teachers' Association of Nigeria (STAN) Biology Panel Series*, 1–6.
- Okeke, E. A. C. (2007). Making science education accessible to all. 23rd inaugural lecture series, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Oyedeji, O. A. (2000). Effective teaching of mathematics. In S. Y. Erinosho, L. A. Adesanya, & A. Ogunyemi (Eds.), *Teaching effectiveness in Nigerian schools* (pp. 1–12). Ibadan: Sam Bookman Publisher.
- Rafiq, S., Afzal, A., & Kamran, F. (2022). Impact of school environment on students' academic achievements at the university level. *VFAST Transactions on Education and Social Sciences*, 10(4), 19–30.
- Ude, V. C., & Onah, E. N. (2017). Influence of ICT as instructional tool in teaching and learning secondary school biology in Enugu South L.G.A., Enugu State. *International Journal of Education*, 2(1), 198–206.
- Ukozor, F. I. (2011). Effect of constructivist teaching strategies on senior secondary school students' achievement and self-efficacy in physics. *African Journal of Science, Technology and Mathematics Education*, 1(1), 141–160.

